

Privacy Compliance Guide Assessment: Connecting the Gaps Between the Laws

Dear participant,

Thank you for taking the time to answer our questionnaire.

This questionnaire is aimed at professionals and researchers working in software development who are familiar with the practices and requirements of the LGPD.

It will take approximately 15 minutes to complete. DECLARATION OF INFORMED

CONSENT

By responding to this survey, you allow the researchers to obtain, use and disclose the anonymous information you provide as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to answer the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this research is completely voluntary and that refusal to participate will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits. If I wish, I can withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that if I decide to participate, I can refuse to answer any questions that I do not feel comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researchers if I have any questions about the research. I understand that my consent will not benefit me directly. I am also aware that the author will keep the data collected in perpetuity and may use it for future academic work.
4. By consenting to participate, I give consent and freely acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as described above, and I give consent to the researchers to use my information to conduct research in the areas mentioned above.

If there are any problems or questions, please send an e-mail to dalle.lucas@aluno.unb.br Thank you for your cooperation.

Sincerely, Lucas

Dalle Rocha.

* Ask a compulsory question

1. Do you agree to take part in this survey? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Skip to question 2

Participant profile

2. Which state are you
from? * Mark *only one*
oval.

Acre

Alagoas

Amapá

Amazonas

Bahia

Ceará

Distrito Federal

Espírito Santo

Goiás

Maranhão

Mato Grosso

Mato Grosso do

Sul Minas Gerais

Pará

Paraíba

Paraná

Pernambuco

Piauí

Rio de Janeiro

Rio Grande do Norte

Rio Grande do Sul

Rondônia

Roraima

Santa Catarina

São Paulo

Sergipe

Tocantins

3. What is your level of education? *

Mark only one oval.

Undergraduate student

Graduate

Specialization

Master's student

Master's

Doctoral student

Doctorate

4. What is your current role in your job? *

Mark only one oval.

Software developer

Software engineer

Requirements analyst

Systems analyst

Project manager

Information security manager

Data officer

Data operator

Data controller

Information security analyst

Other:

5. How many years of experience do you have in Data Privacy? *

Mark only one oval.

Less than 1 year

Between 1 and 5 years

Between 6 and 10 years

Between 11 and 15 years

Over 15 years

6. What is the nature of the organization you work for? *

Mark only one oval.

Private company

Federal Public Administration Agency

Research project/collaboration

State company (BB, CEF, SERPRO, DATAPREV, etc.)

Open source software project

Self-employed

Other: _____

7. Have you ever researched or worked with data protection laws? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

8. Do you currently research or work with data protection laws? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

9. What is your level of experience or knowledge of data protection laws? *

Mark only one oval.

None Basic

Intermediate

Advanced

Access the Privacy Compliance Guide: Connecting the Gaps Between the Laws

Visit this link <https://xdalle.github.io/5L2FGuide/> and read all the contents (Introduction, Scope, Definitions, Principles, Rights, Challenges, About)

10. Mark how much you agree with each sentence. *

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neither disagree nor agree, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree.

Mark only one oval per line.

	1	2	3	4	5
Using the privacy compliance guide would help me comply with data protection laws more quickly.	☐				

Use the privacy compliance guide would take more easy to navigate privacy regulations.	☐				
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Using the privacy compliance guide would help me ensure better protection of users' privacy.	☐				
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Using the privacy compliance guide would help improve the overall efficiency of privacy compliance in my organization.	☐				
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I would use the privacy compliance guide to improve privacy practices in my work.	☐				
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11. Mark how much you agree with each sentence. *

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neither disagree nor agree, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree.

Mark only one oval per line.

	1	2	3	4	5
I find the privacy compliance guide easy to use.	☐				

I find the privacy compliance guide clear and understandable.	☐				
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I find the privacy compliance guide adaptable to different structures and privacy laws (e.g. LGPD, GDPR).	☐				
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I believe that the privacy compliance guide requires a lot of prior knowledge about privacy laws fully understood.	☐				
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12. In your opinion, what are the strengths of the privacy compliance guide? *

13. In your opinion, what are the weaknesses of the privacy compliance guide? *

14. Is there anything you would change in the privacy compliance guide? If so, please explain what you would change.

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